

LAGGING BEHIND IN MENTAL - SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

Azimova Odinakhan

The 18th Specialized Preschool Education Organization under the
Preschool Education Department of Pakhtaabad District, Andijan Region

Abstract : *This article describes the specific features of the speech development of mentally retarded sleepers. Effective ways to eliminate speech defects in mentally retarded sleepers have been revealed.*

Key words: *mentally retarded sleepers, speech development, speech defects, elimination, effective methods, special pedagogy, special school, speech therapy.*

The developing speech is first used as a means of communication, then as a tool for expressing thoughts and thinking, it controls human behavior and activity. The specificity of speech disorders in mentally retarded children is determined by the peculiarities of higher nervous activity and their mental development. According to S. Ya. Rubinstein, the slow development of new differential communication in the brain and the weakness of functional layers in all analyzers are the main reasons for the lack of speech development in mentally retarded children. As a result of the slow development of differentiating conditional connections in the speech-hearing analyzer, a mentally retarded child cannot distinguish speech sounds for a long time, does not understand the words of others, and cannot hear speech clearly. The speech development of mentally retarded children lags behind from the first months. As a result, mentally retarded children of preschool age are not sufficiently formed to engage in activities with objects, phonemic hearing, articulatory apparatus x, activity and interest in the events in the world, x, emotions are not fully manifested, all this has a negative effect on the development of speech.

Speech is considered the most important communication tool of people. But only human beings can swim in their emotions, express their thoughts, convey

interesting information, read poetry, etc. has such possibilities. As a result of such an interaction, when a feeling of reflection and enjoyment of communication occurs, we experience the feeling of empathy, sympathy, mutual understanding .

Improving the speech of a preschool child is very important for his further development and successful study at school. A child who has a good command of speech can express his thoughts well, fully explain and present the material in the textbooks. A child whose speech has developed in accordance with the purpose can express his opinion in a logical sequence, based on reason and self-confidence.

Disruption of the formation and development of various components of the speech system is called general underdevelopment of speech. One of the most urgent tasks of modern speech therapy is to develop effective methods of eliminating speech defects, including preparing children for school .

Identifying mentally retarded children with speech defects in time, classifying existing verbal speech defects and organizing appropriate corrective education not only prevents the appearance of writing and reading defects in these children, but also prevents them from falling behind in the development of program material in the future.

The main tasks of speech development - education of the sound culture of speech, increase of language richness, activity, development of the grammatical side of speech, communication speech are solved in all preschool institutions. The formation of a child's communicative speech is closely related to the grammatical structure of the language, the composition of the language, and the combination of the sound aspect. According to L.S.Volkova, S.N.Shakhovskaya, a group of Kup scientists, it is observed that the grammatical aspects of speech are not formed in mentally retarded children. These agrammatisms (speech disorders expressed in difficulties in constructing sentences or in understanding them) are manifested in difficulties in performing many tasks that require grammatical generalizations. In

this case, the morphological forms of forming and changing words, and the syntactic structure of the sentence are not well formed.

Problems of understanding of some grammatical forms in children with mental retardation of junior school age are covered in the article. Most of the 1st-2nd and 3rd-4th grade students of the assistant school showed that they do not understand the grammatical changes of words. The author experimentally proves that most learners have not developed the understanding of the unity of the lexical meaning of the word and grammatical changes, and recommends some methods that help to eliminate this defect.

Until independence, the educational process of mentally retarded children in our republic's educational institutions was not based on the original programs and textbooks, but on the basis of slightly modified programs and textbooks intended for special institutions of Russia or general educational institutions in Uzbekistan. The practice of a special system was developed irregularly as the work in the system was carried out in this direction.

In the process of developing the grammatical construction of speech in children with mental retardation, each listener should take into account the specific features of the speech development of children with mental retardation, correct existing defects, and develop cognitive processes.

In mother tongue classes, the process of forming grammatical concepts, developing the skills and abilities to use the concepts in practice should be long-term, progress from simple to complex, be organized on the basis of the principles of consistency, and be systematically reinforced and repeated.

It is appropriate to use visual aids that highlight one or another situation in the speaker's narrative to select the real basis for bringing children to practical, visual-figurative, and then conceptual generalizations. The use of the interview method (especially in the initial stages of learning in a special school) is modified in the sense that in the process of using it, it is necessary to include written (written) and

non-verbal (visual) supports. The speakers of the elementary class strictly arrange the language material of their questions and explanations, create conditions for controlling the acceptance of their speeches by the students.

If the use of grammatical or lexical games in the elementary grades of a public school should serve to diversify activities, increase students' interest, and introduce interesting elements, in a special school, these games can serve, first of all, as an effective way of forming speech activity motives. In addition, the lessons can be focused on expanding the practice of speech, understanding the meanings of words, and the relationships between words.

We can conditionally divide the methods used in reading in a special school into two groups: the methods used to form and correct speech and the methods used to study grammar, phonetics, and spelling, which are the same as the methods in the public school. These methods help the learner to strategize (differently) approach to solving different tasks of language learning.

For example, depending on the combination of one or another method with specific tools, we divide the methods into groups: demonstrative (showing, observing, conducting excursions), conversational (conversation, explanation, reading textbook material, etc.) and "mixed" methods (kur-gazmali-suzy methods: observations and explanations of the listener about them, conducting a conversation about the picture, etc.).

Lessons on the formation of the grammatical structure of the language are conducted on the basis of previously prepared lexical material, but the understanding of the lexicon included in the specific lesson material should be checked at the beginning of the lesson. It is necessary to monitor the understanding of the vocabulary by the children who are reading, during the exercise, including when the students are inventing sentences and choosing examples.

Since the main task of practical grammar lessons is to form relevant skills on the basis of bringing students to generalizations, it is good to include various exercises

performed using comparison, analysis and synthesis methods. A typical method used in practical grammar lessons is to create integrated situations that provide a basis for the development and strengthening of students' speaking skills. Their practical implementation depends on the accuracy of formed ideas and concepts, the differentiation of time, space and other symbols.

It should be noted that all these exercises include the students' actions of analyzing the structure (speech, context) along with the composition on the basis of similes. Often, such exercises are constructive in form, but in addition to them, such a task is given, in the performance of which an analytical task is solved. As a result of the process of forming the speech of mentally retarded children from a grammatical point of view, mother tongue education and effective education in general is ensured in a special school.

The choice of the level of speech development as the main factor of integration of mentally retarded children into social life allows to determine the future of the pedagogical process. The developed system for the development of speech proved that it is necessary to implement it only in the conditions of a specially organized communication-subject-developing environment.

In the process of corrective-compensatory and developmental education, it is necessary to approach students differently (stratified) and individually. Work on the development of creative activity, curiosity and worldview of mentally retarded children has confirmed once again that it is an important factor in the formation of their speech. It was determined that a holistic correctional-developmental process, which enables the enrichment of the speech of mentally retarded children and their practical acquisition, should be organized based on a carefully developed plan (projected) by pedagogues and educators, based on the precise definition of the purpose and the measures to influence the learners. In the work, it was proved that the continuation of special measures aimed at the formation of speech in the family

with the help of pedagogues is a necessary condition for the comprehensive development of mentally retarded children and their early integration into social life.

In the process of speech development in pre-school groups in special boarding schools, the individual characteristics of each child are taken into account, and the principle of individual orientation is followed. should take over. In order for speech to be formed as a whole process, it is necessary to work on the integration of different forms of speech activity by children: listening and hearing, speaking, sleeping, and writing. It is recommended to use forms of work that create enthusiasm for spoken communication in the development of children's spoken speech as a means of live communication.

It is necessary to promote the development of alternative programs and technologies that are the basis for improving the correctional-developmental system based on the characteristics of speech and mental development of mentally retarded children. It is necessary to improve the cooperation of pedagogues of preschool groups in special boarding schools with parents . For the parents of mentally retarded children, it is appropriate to develop methodical recommendations on topics related to their children's adaptation to social life, social life and development, and to strengthen educational activities among them in terms of children's social adaptation and speech development.

References:

1. Rubinstein S.Ya. Psychology umstvenno otstalogo shkolnika. - M.: "Prosveshchenie", 1986. - S. 73.
2. Voilokova E.F. Osobennosti ispolzovaniya slov-nozvaniy sensorykh etalonov doshkolnikami s vyrajennoy umstvennoy otstalostyu. // Theoretical and practical problems of the formation of lits with intellectual inadequacy. - St. Petersburg: Izd. RGPU im. A.I. Hertseny, 2000. - S. 38-40.
3. Lisina M.I. Problem ontogenesis obshcheniya. - M.: "Prosveshchenie", 1986. -S. 143.

4. Speech therapy. / Pod ed. L.S. Volkovoy., S.N. Shakhovskoy. - M.: "Vlados", 2003. -S. 46.
5. Fomichyova M.F. Vospitanie u detey pravilnogo proiznoshenia. - M.: "Prosveshchenie", 1989. -S. 56.
6. Mastyukova E.M. Etiology is disordered. // "Logopedia": M., 1998. -S. 123.
7. Smirnova Z.N. Razvitie rechi uchashchikhsya vspomogatelnoy school v svyazi s izucheniem imeni prilagatel'nogo. - M.: "Prosveshchenie", 1990. -S. 67.
8. Nurkeldieva D.A. Methody opredeleniya rechevoy gotovnosti umstvenno otstalyx detey k obucheniyu v shkole. Autoreferat dissertatsii na soiskanie uchenoy stepi kandida pedagogicheskikh nauk. - T.: TGPU im. Nizami, 2001. -S. 21.